

Spectrophotometric and ultrasonic studies of 1 : 1 complex formed by Fe^{III} with 5-aminosalicylic acid and 5-chlorosalicylic acid in the mixed solvent system[†]

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Manuscript received online 06 March 2013, revised 03 May 2013, accepted 13 May 2013

Abstract : The 1 : 1 Fe^{III} complex of 5-aminosalicylic acid and 5-chlorosalicylic acid was studied in the mixed solvent, propanol-2-water (P-2-W) mixture – 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25%, at RTP (298.15 K) using spectrophotometric and ultrasonic technique. The stability constant (K_{CT}) and molar absorptivity (ϵ_{CT}) of the charge transfer complexes (CTCs) formed between Fe^{III} and the ligands were determined simultaneously using spectrophotometric data with the help of a novel graphical method which was developed in this laboratory at RTP. The ultrasonic parameters were also determined in above noted percent composition of the mixed solvent. The changing trends in the ultrasonic parameters were correlated to interpret the molecular interaction in terms of polarity of solvents, hydrogen bonding, charge transfer interactions, dipole-dipole interactions, and Van der Waal forces.

Keywords : Charge transfer complexes, stability constant, molar absorptivity, acoustic parameters, mixed solvent system.

Introduction

The study of metal-ligand equilibria helps in understanding the process through which a metal ion undergoes complex formation in presence of different species in a solution. Factors like pH, concentration of the metal and ligand, and type of solvent etc. influences the composition of a complex. The complexation between metal ions and various organic ligands in solutions comprise a set of reactions and processes in which an important role is played by the components of a liquid medium. In aqueous medium Fe^{III} complexes to many naturally occurring ligands¹ so that the bioavailability of Fe^{III} gets ensured. In that reference the determination of stability constant of complex formed by Fe^{III} with different organic ligands having oxygen in donar site become very important². Ackerman and Hess studied Fe^{III}-phenol complexes and concluded that complex formed is the charge transfer com-

plex³. Therefore, evaluation of stability constant of metal ligand complexes provides an important parameter to study the biologically important natural systems. Several workers have studied charge-transfer complexes spectrophotometrically^{4,5} and confirmed that molecular association is also one of the important reasons for a charge-transfer (CT) complex formation. Spectrophotometry provides an important tool to study the metal-ligand equilibria. Laljee *et al.*^{6,7} have studied various charge transfer chelated complexes of transition and inner transition metals with dyes.

To understand the type of interactions among the components of the complex species in solution, some researchers have used ultrasonic technique⁸. Since ultrasonic technique is highly sensitive and appropriate method to study molecular association or dissociation or even measurement of interactions⁹⁻¹¹. Acoustic parameters are basi-

[†]The paper was presented by Rahul Kumar in the 49th Annual Convention of Chemists for which he was awarded Professor A. K. Dey Memorial Award.

cally related with the binding forces existing among the components (atoms or molecules or charge species) of the solution in understanding the nature of interactions¹²⁻¹⁵. A number of workers have undertaken ultrasonic studies of electrolytic solutions and some of them have carried out it in pure and binary liquids¹⁶⁻²⁰. Deshmukh *et al.* have studied bivalent metal complexes of organic liquids in different mixed solvents ultrasonically²¹.

In present work we have done a systematic study of for Fe^{III}-5-aminosalicylic acid and Fe^{III}-5-chlorosalicylic acid complexes in different proportions of propanol-2-water (P-2-W) binary solvent mixture using both spectrophotometric and ultrasonic techniques. We have determined the stability constant and molar absorptivity simultaneously using spectrophotometric technique. With the help of interferometer (fixed at 2 MHz), acoustic parameters viz. ultrasonic velocity (u), density (ρ), viscosity (η) and derived parameters like adiabatic compressibility (k), free length (L_f), internal pressure (π_i), molar volume (V_m), and acoustic impedance (Z_c) etc. were calculated at room temperature (298.15 K).

Results and discussion

The spectra of 1 : 1 Fe^{III}-5-aminosalicylic acid complex and 1 : 1 Fe^{III}-5-chlorosalicylic acid complex show strong absorption in the visible range with λ_{\max} at 552 nm and 538 nm respectively which do not change by changing the proportions of the components of the solvent mixture. The high values of molar absorptivity reveal that the spectral band is due to the formation of charge-transfer complex. The molar absorptivity depends

on the dielectric constant of the medium²². When the percentage of propanol-2 is varied in the mixed solvent the net dielectric constant of the solvent mixture is also varied which in turn varies the values of the molar absorptivity. Therefore, by changing the percentage of propanol-2, it was observed that the value of molar absorptivity of Fe^{III}-charge transfer complex of 5-aminosalicylic acid and 5-chlorosalicylic acid (Table 1) also changes. Therefore, for the determination of stability constant in medium of different amount of propanol-2 same value of molar absorptivity cannot be used. Hence, the simultaneous determination molar absorptivity and stability constant of charge transfer complex in different percentage of propanol-2, is advantageous.

Different acoustic parameters like ultrasonic velocity, density, viscosity, and different derived parameters, like adiabatic compressibility, free length, internal pressure, molar volume and acoustic impedance etc., for both the complexes in different concentrations of the complex as well as different proportions of the solvent mixture (5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% P-2-W binary mixture at room temperature) have been determined (Tables 2 and 3).

From Figs. 1 and 2, it is clear that the ultrasonic velocity decreases as the metal ion concentration increases because of more complexation in both the cases. With the complexation, density and viscosity of the system increases due to increase in molecular interactions (Figs. 3, 4 and 5, 6). The adiabatic compressibility (k) curve does not show any appreciable change with increasing metal ion concentration. However, the value increases considerably when the proportion of propanol-2 is increased (Figs. 7

Table 1. A comparison of value of $\log K_{CT}$ and ϵ_{CT} for Fe^{III}-5-aminosalicylic acid and Fe^{III}-5-chlorosalicylic acid by spectrophotometric method (Iteration method) in different proportions of propanol-2-water (isopropanol-water) mixed solvent system

Sl. No.	Percent of P-2-W as solvent mixture	Fe ^{III} -5-Aminosalicylic acid complex ($\lambda_{\max} = 552 \text{ nm}$)		Fe ^{III} -5-Chlorosalicylic acid complex ($\lambda_{\max} = 538 \text{ nm}$)	
		Spectrophotometric method ($\log K_{CT}$)	Molar absorptivity ($\epsilon_{CT}) \times 10^{-3}$	Spectrophotometric method ($\log K_{CT}$)	Molar absorptivity ($\epsilon_{CT}) \times 10^{-3}$
1.	5	4.11	2.142	3.05	2.336
2.	10	4.26	2.041	3.29	2.278
3.	15	4.46	1.219	3.57	1.345
4.	20	4.56	1.147	3.77	1.273
5.	25	4.69	1.019	3.86	1.123

Table 2. Change in acoustic parameters-ultrasonic velocity (u), density (ρ), viscosity (η), adiabatic compressibility (k), free length (L_f), internal pressure (π_i), molar volume (V_m) and acoustic impedance (Z_c) for Fe^{III}-5-aminosalicylate complex in the binary mixed solvent propanol-2-water mixture of different proportion ratio at the temperature 298.15 K

Metal Fe ^{III} concentration (M)	Ligand 5-AmSA concentration (L)	u (m/s)	P (kg m ⁻³)	$\eta/10^{-3}$ (Ns/m ²)	$k/10^{-10}$ (kg ⁻¹ ms ⁻²)	$L_f/10^{-11}$ (m)	$\pi_i/10^7$ (atm)	$V_m/10^{-5}$ (m ³ /mole)	$Z_c/10^6$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)
5% Propanol-2-water solvent mixture									
0.001	0.0003	1413.4	1033.8	1.8233	3.4705	4.4009	1.5468	1.9442	1.4611
0.002	0.0003	1411.7	1035.9	1.8269	3.4779	4.4017	1.5515	1.9403	1.4623
0.003	0.0003	1409.1	1037.6	1.8322	3.4830	4.4027	1.5567	1.9371	1.4627
0.004	0.0003	1408.2	1040.1	1.8379	3.4947	4.4038	1.5621	1.9325	1.4646
0.005	0.0003	1406.8	1041.9	1.8421	3.4942	4.4043	1.5665	1.9291	1.4657
10% Propanol-2-water solvent mixture									
0.001	0.0003	1410.3	1030.6	1.8321	3.5404	4.4174	1.5490	2.1540	1.4534
0.002	0.0003	1408.1	1032.1	1.8373	3.5491	4.4211	1.5539	2.1509	1.4540
0.003	0.0003	1407.3	1035.3	1.8435	3.5492	4.4218	1.5601	2.1443	1.4561
0.004	0.0003	1405.7	1037.1	1.8488	3.5542	4.4227	1.5652	2.1405	1.4578
0.005	0.0003	1402.3	1040.0	1.8531	3.5597	4.4236	1.5718	2.1346	1.4583
15% Propanol-2-water solvent mixture									
0.001	0.0003	1408.6	1028.9	1.8432	3.6352	4.4244	1.5530	2.3617	1.4493
0.002	0.0003	1407.1	1031.6	1.8469	3.6450	4.4253	1.5581	2.3555	1.4515
0.003	0.0003	1405.0	1033.3	1.8521	3.6577	4.4283	1.5627	2.3516	1.4547
0.004	0.0003	1404.4	1036.8	1.8576	3.6608	4.4317	1.5720	2.3437	1.4560
0.005	0.0003	1402.1	1039.5	1.8611	3.6633	4.4342	1.5747	2.3376	1.4574
20% Propanol-2-water solvent mixture									
0.001	0.0003	1405.8	1026.9	1.8531	3.6914	4.4395	1.5566	2.5708	1.4436
0.002	0.0003	1404.3	1028.2	1.8583	3.7027	4.4415	1.5610	2.5675	1.4439
0.003	0.0003	1402.1	1030.4	1.8630	3.7128	4.4437	1.5662	2.5621	1.4447
0.004	0.0003	1400.0	1033.6	1.8680	3.7164	4.4449	1.5729	2.5541	1.4470
0.005	0.0003	1397.4	1036.0	1.8729	3.7210	4.4466	1.5788	2.5482	1.4477
25% Propanol-2-water solvent mixture									
0.001	0.0003	1401.6	1024.7	1.8613	3.7693	4.4576	1.5601	2.7813	1.4362
0.002	0.0003	1398.1	1027.3	1.8662	3.7799	4.4631	1.5668	2.7742	1.4367
0.003	0.0003	1396.4	1029.6	1.8721	3.7842	4.4636	1.5726	2.7680	1.4377
0.004	0.0003	1395.2	1032.0	1.8753	3.7945	4.4652	1.5770	2.7616	1.4398
0.005	0.0003	1392.1	1034.8	1.8796	3.7982	4.4661	1.5835	2.7541	1.4405

Table 3. Change in acoustic parameters-ultrasonic velocity (u), density (ρ), viscosity (η), adiabatic compressibility (k), free length (L_f), internal pressure (π_i), molar volume (V_m) and acoustic impedance (Z_c) for Fe^{III}-5-chlorosalicylate complex in the binary mixed solvent propanol-2-water mixture of different proportion ratio at the temperature 298.15 K

Metal Fe ^{III} concentration (M)	Ligand 5-ClISA concentration (L)	u (m/s)	P (kg m ⁻³)	$\eta/10^{-3}$ (Ns/m ²)	$k/10^{-10}$ (kg ⁻¹ ms ⁻²)	$L_f/10^{-11}$ (m)	$\pi_i/10^7$ (atm)	$V_m/10^{-5}$ (m ³ /mole)	$Z_c/10^6$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)
5% Propanol-2-water solvent mixture									
0.001	0.0003	1439.4	1046.8	1.7542	3.4705	4.2911	1.3991	1.9201	1.5067
0.002	0.0003	1438.7	1048.9	1.7596	3.4779	4.2923	1.4022	1.9162	1.5090

Table-3 (contd.)

0.003	0.0003	1437.1	1050.6	1.7640	3.4830	4.2936	1.4064	1.9131	1.5098
0.004	0.0003	1436.2	1054.1	1.7689	3.4947	4.2942	1.4119	1.9068	1.5138
0.005	0.0003	1435.8	1057.9	1.7752	3.4942	4.2948	1.4180	1.8999	1.5189
10% Propanol-2-water solvent mixture									
0.001	0.0003	1435.3	1044.6	1.7602	3.5404	4.3113	1.4004	2.1252	1.4983
0.002	0.0003	1434.1	1045.1	1.7666	3.5491	4.3139	1.4040	2.1241	1.4987
0.003	0.0003	1431.3	1047.3	1.7709	3.5492	4.3148	1.4090	2.1197	1.4990
0.004	0.0003	1430.7	1049.1	1.7755	3.5542	4.3159	1.4139	2.1160	1.5009
0.005	0.0003	1430.1	1054.0	1.7808	3.5597	4.3176	1.4196	2.1062	1.5053
15% Propanol-2-water solvent mixture									
0.001	0.0003	1431.6	1042.9	1.7708	3.6352	4.3260	1.4049	2.3300	1.4910
0.002	0.0003	1429.1	1044.6	1.7758	3.6450	4.3271	1.4096	2.3262	1.4928
0.003	0.0003	1428.0	1046.3	1.7799	3.6577	4.3282	1.4133	2.3224	1.4941
0.004	0.0003	1427.4	1048.8	1.7854	3.6608	4.3289	1.4186	2.3169	1.4970
0.005	0.0003	1427.8	1052.5	1.7898	3.6633	4.3303	1.4229	2.3087	1.5027
20% Propanol-2-water solvent mixture									
0.001	0.0003	1428.8	1040.9	1.7843	3.6914	4.3386	1.4098	2.5362	1.4872
0.002	0.0003	1429.3	1042.2	1.7887	3.7027	4.3395	1.4125	2.5331	1.4896
0.003	0.0003	1427.1	1045.4	1.7940	3.7128	4.3411	1.4185	2.5253	1.4918
0.004	0.0003	1426.0	1048.6	1.7997	3.7164	4.3421	1.4242	2.5176	1.4953
0.005	0.0003	1425.4	1050.0	1.8053	3.7210	4.3430	1.4280	2.5142	1.4976
25% Propanol-2-water solvent mixture									
0.001	0.0003	1425.6	1038.7	1.7911	3.7693	4.3429	1.4121	2.7438	1.4807
0.002	0.0003	1424.1	1040.3	1.7958	3.7799	4.3442	1.4154	2.7395	1.4814
0.003	0.0003	1422.4	1044.6	1.7997	3.7842	4.3462	1.4224	2.7283	1.4838
0.004	0.0003	1420.2	1046.0	1.8053	3.7945	4.3478	1.4270	2.7246	1.4855
0.005	0.0003	1419.1	1049.8	1.8096	3.7982	4.3497	1.4327	2.7148	1.4897

Fig. 1. A plot between ultrasonic velocity vs metal concentration for the $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-5-AmSA}$ in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

Fig. 2. A plot between ultrasonic velocity vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-CISA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

Fig. 3. A plot between density vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-AmSA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

and 8). We know that with the increase in the concentration of propanol-2 in the solvent mixture, the polarity of the solvent decreases, which in turn decreases the extent of hydrogen bonding and net dielectric constant of the medium. This increases the probability of the formation of the complex, that's why free length of the system (intermolecular free length between complex molecule) increases with the proportion of propanol-2 in the solvent mixture (Figs. 9 and 10). Generally for these complex

system internal pressure increases by increasing the propanol-2 content of the solvent mixture as well as metal ion concentration (Figs. 11 and 12). Molar volume, which is the volume, occupied by the one mole of the complex, increases with the complexation (Figs. 13 and 14). Acoustic impedance (Z_c) also increases by increasing the metal ion concentration where as its value decreases by increasing the propanol-2 content of the solvent mixture (Figs. 15 and 16).

Fig. 4. A plot between density vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-CISA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

Fig. 5. A plot between viscosity vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-AmSA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Ferric chloride (BDH), 5-aminosalicylic acid and 5-chlorosalicylic acid (E. Merck) and propanol-2 (E. Merck) all were of AR grade and used as such without any further purification. A digital balance with an accuracy of ± 0.0001 g was used for weighing different solids. For making different standard solutions and mixed solvents double distilled water was used. For attaining the equilib-

rium among the components of the solvent mixture, this is left for about two hours after mixing the components. Ferric chloride undergoes hydrolysis in presence of water so the standard solution of metal ions was prepared in slightly acidic solution ($\text{pH } 2.35 \pm 0.05$). For spectroscopic and ultrasonic measurements, a set of five solutions were prepared in which the concentration of ligands was kept constant (0.0003 mol/L) and the metal ion concentration has varied and kept higher so that only 1 : 1

Fig. 6. A plot between viscosity vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-CISA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

Fig. 7. A plot between adiabatic compressibility vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-AmSA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

species exist in the solution.

The spectra of complexes formed by Fe^{III} with 5-AmSA and 5-CISA in solution from which the λ_{\max} were obtained 552 and 538 respectively. Then the absorbance value of set of five solutions of each complex was measured at respective λ_{\max} using 1.0 cm quartz cell.

The spectra of the set solutions were recorded with double beam spectrophotometer (Systronics Model-2202) using the quartz cell of 1 cm path length.

For ultrasonic measurements, an interferometer was used, working at 2 MHz with an accuracy of $\pm 0.005\%$. For voltage regulation a Volta's stabilizer was used. Tem-

Fig. 8. A plot between adiabatic compressibility vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-CISA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

Fig. 9. A plot between free length vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-AmSA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

perature was maintained with the help of a cryostat with an accuracy of 0.01% and pipes etc. were jacketed with an insulated material.

A double stem capillary type pycnometer (made of borosil glass) having a bulb capacity of $\sim 10 \text{ cm}^3$ was used for density measurement. The capillary with graduated marks had a uniform bore and could be closed by a well-fitting glass cap. Mark calibrations of the pycnometer had done using double distilled water. The uncer-

tainty in density measurements may expect to within $\pm 0.02 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. An Ostwald viscometer with an accuracy of $\pm 0.01\%$ was used for viscosity measurement of the standard solutions, set's solutions and mixed solvents. The viscometer containing the test liquid was allowed to stand for about 30 min in an electronically controlled thermostatic water bath (JULABO Model : ME 31 A) so that the thermal fluctuations in viscometer were minimized. A digital stop watch with accuracy of $\pm 0.03 \text{ s}$ was used for

Fig. 10. A plot between free length vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-CISA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

Fig. 11. A plot between internal pressure vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-AmSA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

the recording of liquid flow time as well as other time recording.

Theory :

Spectrophotometric measurements :

The general reaction for the formation of 1 : 1 complex of Fe^{III} with the bidentate ligand (H₂L) shown to take place as,

where L is a derivative of salicylate bidentate ligand.

The formation constant for the above is expressed by

$$K_{CT} = \frac{[ML]}{[M][H_2L]} \quad (2)$$

For simplification substituting H₂L as L, we can convert

Fig. 12. A plot between internal pressure vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-CISA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

Fig. 13. A plot between molar volume vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-AmSA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

eq. (2) like as

$$K_{CT} = \frac{[ML]}{[M][L]} \quad (3)$$

A number of graphical methods have been developed for

the determination of formation constant of metal complexes²³⁻²⁷. But in these methods one or more parameters have been neglected to get a linear equation²⁸. In this progress we have made a step forward to develop a method in which neither any term is omitted nor any value is left for measurement. So for derivation we have

Fig. 14. A plot between molar volume vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-CISA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

Fig. 15. A plot between acoustic impedance vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-AmSA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

considered the analytical concentrations of metal as well ligands. The method is outlined below :

From the eq. (2), it follows

$$K_{CT} = \frac{[ML]}{[M^0 - [ML]][L^0 - [ML]]} \quad (4)$$

where M⁰ and L⁰ are the analytical concentration of metal ion and ligand respectively. Charges are omitted for the simplification. If metal ion, ligand and complex absorb

light in the region of interest, the absorbance per unit path length can be expressed as

$$A = (M^0 - [ML]) \epsilon_M + [ML] \epsilon_{ML} + (L^0 - [ML]) \epsilon_L \quad (5)$$

where ϵ_M , ϵ_{ML} and ϵ_L are the molar absorptivity of the species M, ML and L respectively.

The eq. (4) can be rearranged as

$$[ML]^2 - [ML] (M^0 + L^0 + 1/K_{CT}) + M^0 L^0 = 0 \quad (6)$$

Fig. 16. A plot between acoustic impedance vs metal concentration for the Fe^{III}-5-CISA in different proportions of propanol-2-water solvent mixture.

From which it follows

$$[ML] = \frac{[M^0 L^0]}{[M^0 + L^0 + 1/K_{CT}]} + \frac{[M^0 L^0]^2}{[M^0 + L^0 + 1/K_{CT}]^3} + \dots \quad (7)$$

If A is the absorbance of the solution under study then for 1 cm path length one can write

$$A = \epsilon [ML]$$

If the higher terms in the eq. (7) are neglected then

$$A = \epsilon M^0 L^0 / [M^0 + L^0 + 1/K_{CT}] \quad (8)$$

The eq. (8) on rearrangement reduced to

$$M^0 L^0 / A = M^0 + L^0 / \epsilon + 1 / \epsilon K_{CT} \quad (9)$$

If $M^0 L^0 / A$ is plotted against $(M^0 + L^0)$ a straight line having slope $1/\epsilon$ and intercept $1/\epsilon K_{CT}$ would obtain.

However if we do not neglect the higher terms then we get the equation.

$$\frac{M^0 L^0}{A} + \frac{A}{\epsilon^2} = \frac{1}{\epsilon} (M^0 + L^0) + \frac{1}{\epsilon K_{CT}} \quad (10)$$

In eq. (10) the value of ϵ is not known and hence a trial value of ϵ can be taken (generally a high value) and the left hand side is plotted against $(M^0 + L^0)$ to get a straight line obtained. By measuring the slope of the graph, molar absorptivity can be calculated which could be refined by successive approximations using a computer program.

Ultrasonic measurements :

Ultrasonic velocity : Nomoto equation²⁹ were for the measurement of ultrasonic velocity of the binary solvent mixture and complex set solutions. The general form of the equation is as

$$u = \sum_{\epsilon=0}^n u_i X^i \quad (1)$$

where $n = 2$ for binary and ternary systems.

Density : Density of the complex solutions have been measured with the help of following equation³⁰,

$$P = M/V + \pi r^2 (h_1 + h_2) \quad (2)$$

where M is the weight of the complex liquid mixture filled in the pycnometer and V is the volume of the bulb. r is the radius of capillary and h_1 and h_2 are the heights of the liquid solution in capillary necks 1 and 2 respectively.

Viscosity : Viscosity of the solutions were measured by using the following Poiseuille's equation,

$$\eta = \pi h r g r^4 t / 8 L V = \rho \beta t \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the density of the solution, h is the height of the column of the solution, g is acceleration due to gravity, and r is the radius of the flow pipe. L is the length and t is the time of fall of solution.

Adiabatic compressibility : The adiabatic compressibility (k) of the solutions was derived from the following equations,

$$k = 1/u^2 \rho \quad (4)$$

where u is the ultrasonic velocity and ρ is the density of the complex solution.

Free length : The intermolecular free length (L_f) was calculated with the help of following equation,

$$L_f = K/u \rho^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where K is the temperature dependent constant ($K = 2.0 \times 10^{-6}$ at 298.15 K), ρ is the density of the solutions and u ultrasonic velocity of the solution.

Internal pressure : Internal pressure of the complex solutions was measured using following equation,

$$\pi_i = bRT [K\eta/u]^{1/2} [\rho^{2/3}/M_{\text{eff}}^{7/6}] \quad (6)$$

where b stands for the cubic packing factor which is assumed to be 2 for liquids, K is the temperature dependent constant (4.28×10^9 at 298.15 K), where as T is the temperature on absolute scale. M_{eff} is the effective molecular weight of the complex liquid mixture.

Molar volume : The molar volume (V_m) of the ternary mixture was calculated from the following eq. (7),

$$V_m = [X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2 + X_3 M_3]/\rho \quad (7)$$

whereas X_1 , X_2 , X_3 and M_1 , M_2 , M_3 are mole fractions and molecular weights of components 1, 2, 3, respectively.

Acoustic impedance : Acoustic impedance is the product of ultrasonic velocity and density of the solution,

$$Z = u_s \cdot \rho_s \quad (8)$$

where Z is acoustic impedance and u_s , ρ_s are ultrasonic velocity and density of the solutions respectively.

Conclusion

We have successfully done the systematic studies on the 1 : 1 Fe^{III} complex of 5-aminosalicylic acid and 5-chlorosalicylic acid in the mixed solvent, propanol-2-water mixture (P-2-W) – 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25%, at RTP (298.15 K) using both spectrophotometric and ultrasonic methods. It is concluded that in acidic medium and with higher metal ion concentration only 1 : 1 Fe^{III} complex of 5-aminosalicylic acid and 5-chlorosalicylic acid are formed, whose stability constant (SC) and molar absorptivity coefficient (ϵ) of charge transfer (CT) complexes were determined simultaneously with the help of novel

graphical method and computational method developed in our laboratory. The stability constant values of CT complexes were changed as the proportion of propanol-2 was increased in the solution in the order : 5% < 10% < 15% < 20% < 25%. Further, the acoustic parameters were also calculated in order to study the molecular interactions. This study conclusively established that as the percentage of 2-propanol is increased in binary solvent mixture, the ultrasonic velocity decreases, while density, viscosity, free length, internal pressure and molar volume of the system increases. Acoustic impedance (Z_c) also increases with increasing metal ion concentration where as its value decreases by increasing the propanol-2 content of the solvent mixture.

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